

Second harmonic response of azobenzene self-assembled monolayers: the effect of push/pull substitution

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Abstract

A computational methodology combining classical molecular dynamic simulations (MD) and density functional theory (DFT) calculations is employed to characterize the second harmonic generation (SHG) response of self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) functionalized with azobenzene photochromic units. Chemical substitution of the azobenzene core is explored to investigate how the nature of the substituent influences the morphology and nonlinear optical properties (NLO) of the SAMs. The interfacial NLO responses are computed accounting for the effect of structural fluctuations and steric interactions of individual azobenzene units, as well as electrostatic intermolecular interactions. It turns out that the para functionalization of the terminal phenyl of azobenzene core with an electron-acceptor group is promising for applications, since

it enhances the NLO contrast perpendicular to the surface with respect to the non-substituted system, while maintaining well-separated SHG signal ranges for the two E and Z isomeric forms, making them easily distinguishable for polarization-resolved SHG measurements.

1 Introduction

Over the last few decades, surface modification by chemical functionalization has made significant progress, mainly due to new developments in monolayer engineering. Different strategies exist to functionalize solid supports, ranging from molecular deposition via spin-coating techniques, creation of Langmuir-Blodgett (LB) films,¹ in which the only requirement for the molecules is to have an amphiphilic character, or preparation of Self-Assembled Monolayers (SAMs), in which molecules are grafted on the surface.² The term self-assembled monolayers is indeed used to describe organized molecular assemblies formed spontaneously, owing to favorable intermolecular interactions and to chemical bonding between each molecular component and a solid substrate. These interactions are also responsible for maintaining the stability of the whole assembly, ensuring large structural and orientational control. Moreover, SAMs can be used to bring new functionalities to the surface. In particular, monolayers functionalized with photo-responsive units enable fine modulation of the surface structure and properties, ranging from chemical reactivity to optical activity, with applications in photonics, electro-optics or chemical detection.^{3,4}

A representative example of interconnection between macroscopic interfacial properties and molecular-scale structural and electronic properties in 2D materials is the photoinduced change in wettability of thin films of amorphous co-polymer coupled with azobenzene or spiropyran photoswitches.⁵ The increased wettability of the surfaces observed after irradiation in these systems was rationalized by the change in the directionality of the molecular dipole moments with respect to the surface normal. Interface modification with photoreponsive SAMs is also an effective route for developing functional electronic devices such

as organic field-effect transistors (OFETs), as it enables the reversible photocontrol of the charge carrier density at the interface.⁶⁻⁸ In recent advances in biotechnology, the fabrication of smart biological surfaces in which the control of surface properties is induced by different external stimuli is mainly converging toward the use of SAMs. Indeed, SAMs can be used to promote selective adsorption of proteins, forming biochemically reactive surfaces that offer intriguing possibilities for new smart surfaces and biological sensors.⁹

SAMs functionalized with nonlinear optical (NLO) photoswitches, i.e. photochromic units exhibiting large contrast in their second-harmonic (SH) signal, are also interesting for use in optical memory devices, as their SH response can be probed upon irradiation in the near-IR range, which is not energetic enough to trigger uncontrolled photo-isomerizations, and thus confers a non-destructive readout ability to the device. In this context, the reversible photoswitching of interfacial SH responses was demonstrated by Tegeder and collaborators, after functionalization of gold or silica surfaces with either fulgimide¹⁰ or azobenzene¹¹ derivatives. During alternating illumination steps with UV and visible light, inducing *trans-cis* and *cis-trans* photoisomerization cycles, azobenzene-based SAMs showed variations in NLO response of around 20% without marked material fatigue.

In addition to surface engineering, the design of optimal light-responsive NLO materials and the optimization of their performances in terms of photocommutation efficiency and SH contrast amplitude relies on computational approaches capable of providing a microscopic description of the interfacial molecular organization and able to link it to macroscopic material properties. In this context, mixed quantum/classical computational methodologies coupling molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with density functional theory (DFT) calculations have been successfully used to rationalize the NLO response of photochromic systems,¹² both in solution¹³⁻²² and after anchoring on solid substrates.^{23,24} In particular, such MD+DFT schemes were applied to photoresponsive SAMs constituted of azobenzene photoswitches grafted onto amorphous SiO₂ surfaces with different functionalization ratios.²⁴ MD simulations provided the morphology of the SAMs with atomic detail, and revealed a

decreasing *trans-cis* photoisomerization yield with increasing chromophore concentration, in accordance with experimental observations. The calculations also evidenced drastic changes in the morphology of the SAM upon photoisomerization, although a high degree of structural disorder is present in both isomerization states. This disorder resulted in broad distributions of the first hyperpolarizability (β) of the molecular units, especially in the *cis* form, where the terminal phenyl ring adopts random orientations. Unfortunately, for this system, the $\beta(\textit{trans})/\beta(\textit{cis})$ SH contrast observed upon photoisomerization, besides being dependent on chromophore concentration, remains quite weak in simulations and experiments.

To identify a strategy for enhancing the contrast, we apply here the same computational approach to unravel the impact of chemical substitution of azobenzene units with an electron-withdrawing (EWG, or acceptor A) or an electron-donating group (EDG, or donor D) on the NLO responses of the SAM. More specifically, the influence on the interface structure of $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{NH}_2$ groups grafted in *para* position of the azobenzene terminal phenyl is first analyzed in both isomeric states of the SAM and compared to that of the reference unsubstituted system. Next, DFT calculations are used to obtain a molecular interpretation of how chemical substitution affects the SHG responses of both SAM states, as well as the NLO contrast upon photocommutation.

2 Computational approach

In this work we adopted a computational MD+DFT scheme to simulate the second order NLO properties of R-substituted azobenzene-based SAMs, where R is either the electron-withdrawing ($-\text{NO}_2$) or the electron-donating ($-\text{NH}_2$) group. DFT calculations were carried out using the Gaussian16 package.²⁵ MD simulations were performed using the NAMD software in the Canonical ensemble (NVT) using Periodic Boundary Condition (PBC). The simulation box used for the dynamics of SAM samples is an orthorhombic box with dimensions $a = 52.044 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 51.119 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 150.000 \text{ \AA}$. Long-range electrostatic interactions and

van der Waals interactions are included for atoms separated by three bonds (1-4 interactions), with scaling factors of 0.833 and 0.5, respectively. During the simulations, a slab of 20 Å at the bottom part of the silica surface was kept frozen.

2.1 Chemical structure of the self-assembled monolayers

The investigated SAMs contain 121 densely-packed dodecylsilanol chains anchored onto an amorphous silica surface with a coverage of 4.55 molecules/nm². The dodecylsilanol spacers serve as a basis for grafting the azobenzene units, and also to decouple the photochromic layer from the solid substrate, in order to preserve the photoswitching properties.¹¹ In this work, we only consider SAMs with a 50% functionalization ratio (i.e. azobenzene molecules are grafted onto only 61 of the 121 alkyl chains for a coverage of 2.29 molecules/nm²), as this relative concentration was shown to allow achieving the highest photoisomerization yield.²⁴ The non-functionalized alkyl chains are referred to as C12, and the functionalized ones are named according to the nature of the substitution on the azobenzene moiety: AZO-H refers to the alkoxy-azobenzene SAM studied in reference 24, while AZO-A labels the system with a nitro group (-NO₂) replacing the 4' hydrogen, and AZO-D that with terminal amine group (-NH₂). The *trans* or *cis* conformation of the azobenzene moiety is instead indicated in parenthesis using the E/Z nomenclature. As an example, the donor-substituted system in its *cis* state is referred to as AZO-D(Z). The chemical structure of investigated systems, together with the nomenclature used throughout this report, are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: a) Sketch of the self-assembled monolayer (SAM); b) Chemical structures of the investigated systems: unsubstituted alkyl chain (C12), chromophore-functionalized chains with AZO-H bearing a pristine azobenzene unit, and AZO-D and AZO-A the donor (R = NH₂) and acceptor (R = NO₂) substituted derivatives. The θ_1 - θ_5 dihedrals are also displayed; c) Simulation box and details of the components of the system highlighted in different colors for the case of AZO-A(E). The functionalized chains (AZO-A(E)) are represented in red while the alkyl chains (C12) appear in gray.

2.2 Parametrization of the Force Field

The donor and acceptor substituted azobenzene molecules were modeled using a modified version of the General AMBER Force Field (GAFF)²⁶ for which specific parameters were optimized to correctly describe the main geometric features of the systems. Namely, electrostatic potential-fitted (ESP) charges and torsional force field parameters of relevant dihedral angles were obtained from DFT calculations at the M06/6-311G(d) level, while bond equilibrium distances were adjusted to match those of the DFT optimized geometry. In these calculations, the alkyl chain of the AZO units was truncated to (CH₂)₂-CH₃ to avoid considering the manifold of conformers arising from a long flexible chain. To parametrize the dihedrals of the *trans* and *cis*-azobenzene systems, we followed the procedure reported in the reference study (Ref. 24) with the methodology described in Ref. 27, which relies on the

adapting biasing force (ABF)²⁸ technique. For θ_1 - θ_5 , the variation of the DFT energy as a function of the torsional angle was calculated with constrained energy minimizations for dihedral values ranging from 0 to 180 degrees with a step interval of 10 degrees. Instead, for the torsion around the N=N double bond (θ_{azo} in Figure 1b), both the ground (S_0) and excited state (S_1) were parametrized using literature results obtained at the CASPT2 *ab initio* level.²⁹ The reparametrization of the bond lengths was done in an iterative fashion with that of the dihedral angles until convergence was reached. All data relative to the details of the parameterization procedure are reported in the Supporting Information (SI). Building on the work reported in the reference study (Ref. 24), the silicon and oxygen atoms of the amorphous silica surface were described with the Clay Force Field³⁰ and the parameters for the non-functionalized C12 alkyl chains were used without further modifications.

2.3 Preparation of the *trans* SAMs

AZO-A(E) and AZO-D(E) SAMs morphologies were obtained starting from the structures derived in the reference study of the AZO-H system.²⁴ Therein, a SAM of C12 was equilibrated prior to grafting azobenzene units with increasing functionalization ratio (50%, 75% and 100%) and the resulting azobenzene-based SAMs were then annealed and equilibrated. Here, starting from the non-equilibrated AZO-H(E) SAM at 50% functionalization ratio, the terminal H atom of the azobenzene moiety of each AZO-H(E) molecule has been replaced by either -NO₂ or -NH₂ groups to produce the initial configuration of the AZO-A(E) and AZO-D(E) systems, respectively. Then, a minimization was performed to relax the system after the chemical change induced by replacing the 4' hydrogen. Figure 1c illustrates the final sample in the case of AZO-A(E) as an example, with the size of the simulation box and the different components of the system. The same box size was used in all simulations.

2.4 Obtaining the *cis*-layer

Starting from the equilibrated *trans* SAMs, the *cis* samples were obtained using the iterative photoisomerization procedure described in Ref 31. The central idea of this strategy is to model classically the *trans*-to-*cis* photoswitching, considering only the torsional mechanism around θ_{azo} and using two distinct FFs for the ground (S_0) and excited (S_1) states for this angle. The objective of this procedure is not to accurately model the photoisomerization process, but rather to generate a realistic morphology of the *cis*-layer starting from the equilibrated *trans* SAM. The isomerization is realized with two iterative steps, schematized in Figure 2a. The first (A) simulates the excitation of the *trans* isomer to the low-lying excited state, S_1 . This is achieved by switching the force field from that parameterized for S_0 to the one parameterized for S_1 and conducting a MD simulation of 1 ns at 300 K, leaving the *trans* isomers to rearrange their geometries following the S_1 potential energy surface. The second step (B) simulates the relaxation after the decay from S_1 , and it is realized by switching back to the FF of the ground state in a very short (0.01 ns) MD simulation (see the supporting information of Ref. 24 for the convergence in steps A and B for the non-substituted system). Two possible pathways can be taken, with the azobenzene moiety either evolving towards the *cis* isomer or going back to the initial *trans* conformation. Steps A and B are repeated either until all molecules have switched to their *cis* form, or after 10 consecutive iterations in which no new molecules have switched. The results of the evolution of the photoswitching from the *trans* to the *cis* layer are reported in Figure 2b for both donor and acceptor substituted systems, i.e. AZO-A(E) \rightarrow AZO-A(Z) and AZO-D(E) \rightarrow AZO-D(Z). At convergence, photoisomerization yields of 95% were achieved for both systems, with thus no impact of the terminal substituent: in both *cis* SAMs, only three residues did not switch to their *cis* form. Nevertheless, the switching process from AZO-A(E) to AZO-A(Z) was faster and stopped after the 34th cycle due to 10 consecutive unsuccessful iterations, while for AZO-D the process stopped after 43 cycles.

Figure 2: a) Graphical scheme of the photoswitching procedure; b) Percentage of *trans* residues that switched to *cis* along the iterative photoswitching process sketched in a) for both the AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs. A cycle corresponds to the steps A + B.

2.5 Molecular dynamics simulations of *trans* and *cis* SAMs

Once the SAM samples were prepared as described in the previous sections, both *trans* and *cis*-layers were annealed for 60 ns at 400 K before equilibration at 300 K for 30 ns. Then, a production run of 10 ns at 300 K was performed, from which selected frames were extracted at regular time steps for subsequent analysis. As discussed below, different structural properties were evaluated to characterize the morphology of the *trans* and *cis*-layers of AZO-D and AZO-A, averaging over 1000 configurations (see details and Figure S9 in SI).

2.6 Computation of the NLO responses

NLO properties were computed at the DFT level with the M06-2X exchange-correlation functional and the 6-311+G(d) basis set. The same level of calculation was used in the previous study on non-substituted azobenzenes,²⁴ enabling a direct comparison of the results. In practice, 10 frames were extracted from the production runs of both *trans* and *cis* SAMs of AZO-A and AZO-D. The geometries of AZO-R molecules were then extracted from each frame, yielding a total of 610 molecular residues per SAM (including the 5% of unswitched molecules in the case of the AZO-R(Z) samples), allowing temporal and spatial sampling

of electronic properties. In these calculations, the terminal $-\text{Si}(\text{OH})_2$ moiety was removed to reduce the computational cost without loss of accuracy, as the anchoring group has a negligible impact on the hyperpolarizability (see SI section 4.2).

The interfacial NLO response was analyzed by calculating, for each molecular fragment, the norm of the first hyperpolarizability vector:

$$\beta = \sqrt{\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2 + \beta_z^2} \quad (1)$$

with components defined as:

$$\beta_j = \frac{1}{3} \sum_i (\beta_{ijj} + \beta_{jij} + \beta_{jji}) \quad (2)$$

with $i, j = x, y, z$ the axes of the simulation box - see Figure 1c. In addition, the anisotropy a_β of the NLO response of the molecular fragments was also quantified, by calculating the ratio between the hyperpolarizability vector components normal and parallel to the surface:

$$a_\beta = \frac{|\beta_z|}{\sqrt{\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2}} \quad (3)$$

Both static and frequency-dependent (dynamic) NLO responses were calculated. In the latter case, the second harmonic generation (SHG) process $\beta(-2\omega; \omega, \omega)$ was considered, using an incident wavelength $\lambda_{inc} = 2\pi c/\omega$ of 800 nm. In a first step, NLO properties were calculated on the isolated residues: this approach captures the effects of the conformational dynamics of the individual fragments, but does not account for any electrostatic intermolecular interaction. In a second step, these interactions were included in the DFT calculations by applying, around the central target chromophore, an electrostatic embedding constituted of ESP point charges (PCs) at the atomic positions of neighboring chromophores. The size of the PC-embedding was set using a cutoff radius r_5 equal to 35 Å, which includes up to the fifth molecular neighbors. Every molecule having the center of mass of the ALK moiety

at a distance $r < r_5$ is included in the PC-Embedding. This radius was shown in Ref. 24 to be large enough to achieve the convergence of the calculated NLO responses. Among the 610 molecular geometries analyzed for each SAM sample, some structures provided huge dynamic β values (> 200000 a.u.) due to large frequency resonance effects. These structures were considered as outliers and omitted from the analysis.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Structural analysis of the SAMs

The lateral and top views of the structures in their equilibrated morphologies are shown in Figure 3, clearly revealing the crystalline order of the alkyl chains in contrast with the disordered and tilted organization of the chromophores.

Figure 3: Lateral and top views of SAM-samples in the *trans* and *cis*-layer, where only the mobile section of the SiO₂ substrate is shown.

Therefore, alkyl chains, chromophore moieties and unsubstituted chains, hereafter referred to as ALK, AZO and C12, were distinguished in the structural analysis. We first

characterized the positional order of the molecular fragments within the SAMs by analyzing their respective two-dimensional density of neighbors ($N(x, y)$), which gives the probability that the center of mass of a molecule, projected in the (x, y) plane, is at a given position with respect to that of a central reference molecule (Figures 4b and S10). A characteristic ordering of alkylosiloxane SAMs has been reported in the literature,³² where a hexagonal packing has been observed. As shown in the 2D neighbor densities of the alkyl chains, the hexagonal pattern is preserved after AZO-functionalization of the SAMs, regardless of the *trans* or *cis* conformation of the azobenzene moiety and the nature of the terminal -R substituent. However, as clearly seen in the top panels of Figures 4b and S10, this hexagonal order is not retained in the upper part of the SAM, where the substituted azobenzene moieties exhibit significant positional disorder, preventing the identification of a specific 2D lattice.

The identification of the characteristic intermolecular distances can be more easily captured by the one-dimensional density of neighbors, showing the number of neighbors $N(r_{xy})$ as a function of the in-plane distance r_{xy} between their centers of mass. In particular, the peaks in the $N(r_{xy})$ function for a crystalline system provide the lattice parameters. The first peak represents the nearest-neighbor distance, i.e. the preferred distance between molecular residues of same type, which derives from the lattice structure of the SAM. Figure 4a reports such distributions for the non-functionalized (C12) and functionalized (ALK) alkyl chains in the different SAM samples. It can be seen that the C12 and ALK chains share the same lattice parameter, with nearly identical nearest-neighbor distances of about 5 Å. On the other hand, the 1D neighbor densities of the top sublayer of AZO-A and AZO-D (Figure 4a, top) do not show marked peaks due to the high positional disorder of the AZO residues. The broad first peak for E isomers shows that nearest AZO neighbors are more frequently found at distances lying between 5.5 Å and 6.5 Å. In contrast, the distribution becomes even broader for Z isomers and shorter distances may occur, mainly due to the Z molecular shape for which the center of mass may lie outside the volume actually occupied by the chromophore.

Figure 4: Left: 1D neighbor densities of the non-functionalized alkyl chains (C12, bottom) the functionalized alkyl chains (ALK, middle), and the AZO cores (top) of the AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs in their *trans* (E) and *cis* (Z) states. Right: 2D neighbor densities of the azobenzene moieties (top) and of the alkyl chain (bottom) for the AZO-A(E) SAM. See Figure S10 for the 2D neighbor densities of all SAMs.

Turning to the analysis of the orientational order of the molecular fragments, we first evaluated the nematic order parameter S , defined as $S = \langle P_2 \rangle = \frac{3}{2} \cos^2 \phi - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{3}{2} \langle \vec{n} \cdot \vec{u} \rangle - \frac{1}{2}$, with ϕ the angle between the long molecular axis (\vec{u}) and the direction of maximum alignment (\vec{n}). A value of 1 ($\langle \phi \rangle = 0$) indicates perfect alignment, while a value of 0 ($\langle \phi \rangle \simeq 54.7^\circ$, the so-called magic angle) characterizes a completely random orientation. Again, we analyzed separately the orientational order of the bottom and top sub-layers of the SAMs, evaluating two nematic order parameters, S_{ALK} and S_{AZO} , with the ϕ angle referring to the orientation of the alkyl chains (ALK) and of the azobenzene cores (AZO), respectively, identified with the orientation of the principal inertia axis with lowest eigenvalue.

As shown in Table 1, the S values are consistent with those calculated for the non-substituted AZO-H SAMs.²⁴ More specifically, the ALK part of the SAMs exhibits high orientational order, with S_{ALK} values of about 0.9, while the AZO top layers present significant disorder indicated by low S_{AZO} values. This can be traced back to the loose packing of the chromophores associated with the 50% functionalization ratio, which allows for the azobenzene moieties to lie down with no particular orientation. This is notably illustrated by the average tilt angles $\langle\theta_{ALK}\rangle$ and $\langle\theta_{AZO}\rangle$, which define the orientation of the ALK and AZO fragments with respect to the normal to the surface, whose distributions are given in Figure 5. While for AZO-D the alkyl chains maintain an upright tilted orientation deviating from the normal (by about 14-16° on average), some of the chains are perfectly vertical in AZO-A and the distribution of $\cos\theta_{ALK}$ is peaked at 1. Conversely, the AZO chromophores show a broad distribution of tilt angles, which becomes even broader for Z isomers. However, the distributions of $\cos\theta_{AZO}$ vary with the terminal substituent: in the presence of nitro group the probability to find negative $\cos\theta_{azo}$ values is non zero for the Z isomer, indicating that a few residues have the AZO core globally pointing down toward the surface. Overall, the AZO-D groups present a more vertical orientation than the AZO-A groups. This is reflected by the higher thickness and roughness of the AZO-D films, reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Nematic order parameter (S) and average tilt angle (θ , degrees) for the ALK and AZO sub-layers in the AZO-H, AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs in their *trans* (E) and *cis* (Z) states, as well as average values of the thickness and surface roughness of the SAMs (in Å).

	AZO-H(E)*	AZO-H(Z)*	AZO-A(E)	AZO-A(Z)	AZO-D(E)	AZO-D(Z)
S_{ALK}	0.865	0.854	0.889	0.885	0.851	0.867
S_{AZO}	0.114	0.058	0.214	0.148	0.031	0.099
$\langle\theta_{ALK}\rangle$	14 ± 7	15 ± 7	14 ± 7	14 ± 6	16 ± 6	17 ± 7
$\langle\theta_{AZO}\rangle$	41 ± 16	38 ± 17	56 ± 12	65 ± 16	43 ± 17	46 ± 15
Thickness	24.5	23.6	20.8	17.8	22.5	20.3
Roughness	2.19	1.26	1.49	1.30	2.82	1.75

* Values taken from Ref 24.

Figure 5: Distribution of tilt angles θ_{ALK} and θ_{AZO} in the AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs. The definition of the angles, which characterize the orientation of the ALK and AZO moieties with respect to the box z -axis normal to the surface, is illustrated on the right.

A deeper understanding of the morphological changes caused by photoisomerization can be achieved by distinctly considering the orientational distributions of the two azobenzene phenyl rings (θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2}). As shown in Figure 6, the distributions θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} are quasi-superimposable in both *trans* SAMs, indicating that the axes of the two phenyl rings are almost parallel as expected, though the shape of the distributions in D and A are different, reflecting what already observed for θ_{AZO} .

In contrast, in the *cis* SAMs, the distributions of θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} differ significantly: the first is peaked around 1, meaning that the azo-phenyl ring connected to the alkyl chain adopts a more vertical orientation after the photoisomerization. Reversely, θ_{Ph2} displays very broad distributions, indicating that the terminal phenyl is randomly oriented. Moreover, the negative $\cos\theta_{Ph2}$ values found in AZO-D(Z) imply that some AZO residues have their terminal phenyl pointing down toward the surface. This effect is even more marked in AZO-A(Z), indicating that the Z isomers inherit at least in part their orientation from the corresponding E isomers.

Figure 6: Distribution of tilt angles of the phenyl groups in the two isomers of AZO-A on the left and of AZO-D SAMs on the right. θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} are defined considering the atoms shown in color, as schematized on the right.

3.2 Surface dipole

Prior to investigating their NLO responses, we monitored the interfacial dipole of the different SAMs, using the same 610 structures extracted from the MD trajectories (see section 2.6). For each molecular residue, we computed the norm of the dipole moment μ , its component normal to the surface (μ_z), the in-plane component ($\mu_{\parallel} = \sqrt{\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2}$) and the dipolar anisotropy, defined as $a_{\mu} = |\mu_z|/\mu_{\parallel}$. The distributions of the μ , μ_z and a_{μ} values of the AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs in their *trans* and *cis* forms are plotted in Figure 7, while average values and standard deviations are given in Table 2. All these quantities show broad distributions resulting from the conformational and orientational disorder of the AZO cores. Despite significant geometrical fluctuations, the average dipole moment of AZO units extracted from AZO-A(E) and AZO-A(Z) SAMs slightly decreases compared to the dipole moment of isolated molecules in their equilibrium geometry (μ_{eq} in Table 2), while it shows a modest increase for AZO-D SAMs. In *trans* SAMs, changing the electronic character of the R group from AZO-A(E) to AZO-D(E) reverses the direction of the dipole moment vector. Indeed, the distribution and average of μ_z values indicate that the molecular dipoles in AZO-A(E) are mainly directed towards the surface, whereas in AZO-D(E) they are directed outwards. The AZO-A(E) and AZO-D(E) SAMs also exhibit very different dipolar anisotropy; the average a_{μ} value of the AZO-A(E) is much lower than one, indicating that

the in-plane components of the dipole vector dominate, while the out-of-plane component is instead the major one in AZO-D(E). The opposite occurs for Z conformers. However, the very small μ_z value found for AZO-D(Z) reveals that the molecular dipoles are primarily aligned parallel to the surface, which is reflected by the low value of the anisotropy factor.

Figure 7: Probability distribution of the norm (a) and the z -component (b) of the molecular dipole (in Debye), and of the dipolar anisotropy (c) in the different monolayers.

Table 2: Dipole moment of the AZO units in their equilibrium geometry (μ_{eq}); average values and standard deviations of the norm (μ), z -component (μ_z) and in-plane component ($\mu_{||}$) of the molecular dipole, and dipolar anisotropy (a_μ) of the AZO units extracted from the different monolayers. All dipoles are given in Debye.

	μ_{eq}	μ	μ_z	$\mu_{ }$	a_μ
AZO-A(E)	8.58	7.61 ± 0.74	-3.39 ± 1.54	6.58 ± 1.11	0.57 ± 0.40
AZO-A(Z)	6.58	4.95 ± 1.44	-1.83 ± 2.06	4.02 ± 1.67	1.00 ± 2.78
AZO-D(E)	1.66	2.37 ± 0.71	1.15 ± 1.15	1.72 ± 0.73	1.21 ± 2.08
AZO-D(Z)	4.81	4.87 ± 1.07	-0.16 ± 2.18	4.32 ± 1.21	0.53 ± 0.72

As illustrated in Figure 8, the differences in the magnitude and orientation of the molecular dipoles in the SAMs lead to different electrostatic potentials $V(z)$ along the z axis normal to the surface. $V(z)$ was evaluated by applying the one-dimensional Poisson equation and numerically integrating twice the total charge density $\rho(z)$ along the z direction, and by setting the vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 to 1. The charge density $\rho(z)$ was calculated as the histogram of atomic partial charges averaged in vertical slabs parallel to the silica surface (see Ref. 33 for details). In practice, the simulated sample is treated as an infinitely extended 2D layer of point charges, in which the potential fluctuates and reaches a constant value on the two sides.³⁴ The overall voltage change produced by the different SAMs is then evaluated

as the difference between the plateau values (V_s) of the potential at the top of the surface ($z > 60 \text{ \AA}$), using as reference the potential of the bare SiO_2 substrate in the absence of SAM.

Due to its normal dipole ($\vec{\mu}_z$, see Table 2) pointing away from the surface, AZO-D(E) shows the largest V_s value. AZO-A(E), on the other hand, has the lowest value of V_s , as $\vec{\mu}_z$ is large and points towards the silica surface. Photoisomerization of AZO-D induces a decrease of the electrostatic potential by 1.23 V, resulting from the almost cancellation of the normal surface dipole in the Z form. Reversely, the $\text{E} \rightarrow \text{Z}$ photochromic reaction shifts upward the V_s potential of AZO-A by 1.30 V, as a result of the lowering of the $\vec{\mu}_z$ norm.

Figure 8: Electric potential along z -axis across the SAMs, where $0 < z < 30$ corresponds to the SiO_2 substrate and $30 < z < 60$ to the organic part. The zero of the potential is arbitrarily set to the plateau value calculated for the SiO_2 substrate in the absence of SAM (black line).

3.3 Nonlinear optical properties

3.3.1 NLO responses of DFT optimized AZO-A and AZO-D molecules

We begin with the discussion of the impact of chemical substitution on the hyperpolarizabilities of the molecules at their optimized gas phase equilibrium geometries. The β values reported in Table 3 show that adding a donor or acceptor group on the terminal phenyl dramatically changes not only the permanent dipole but also the static first hyperpolarizability

of E isomers of AZO-A and AZO-D compared to the non-substituted AZO-H(E) molecule. In particular, adding an electron-withdrawing $-\text{NO}_2$ group largely enhances the hyperpolarizability, while the NLO response significantly drops upon $-\text{NH}_2$ substitution. The low β value of AZO-D(E) arises from the compensation of the π -electron donating characters of $-\text{NH}_2$ and of the ether oxygen placed at the opposite side of the azobenzene core. Upon photoisomerization, the β value of AZO-A significantly decreases, while it increases for AZO-D, resulting in $\eta = \beta(E)/\beta(Z)$ contrasts of 2.9 and 0.5, respectively. In the dynamic regime, the β contrast of AZO-A rises to 5.6, while that of AZO-D becomes larger than unity ($\eta = 1.7$). This can be explained by the more intense absorption of the *trans* form with respect to the *cis* in the $\lambda_{inc}/2 = 400$ nm region, which causes larger frequency dispersion effects (see the simulated absorption spectra in Figure S8).

3.3.2 NLO responses of the SAMs

The importance of considering positional and conformational disorder in addressing the NLO response of self-assembled monolayer is immediately evident from the probability distributions of the static and dynamic NLO responses, namely β , β_z and a_β values of individual AZO-A and AZO-D fragments, plotted in Figures S15 and 9, and from average values and standard deviations reported in Table 3.

Figure 9: Distributions of the dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) β , β_z and a_β values in the different monolayers, obtained without electrostatic embedding. Average values and standard deviations are reported. Dashed vertical lines correspond to the β responses of the chromophores calculated at their gas phase equilibrium geometries.

Table 3: Average values and standard deviations of the static ($\lambda_{inc} = \infty$) and dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) NLO responses β , β_z and a_β calculated on AZO molecular residues for the different monolayers without electrostatic embedding, and hyperpolarizability contrasts, defined as $\eta = \beta(E)/\beta(Z)$ and $\eta_z = \beta_z(E)/\beta_z(Z)$. The β and η values calculated for the AZO residues in their equilibrium geometries optimized at the M06/6-311G(d) level are also reported for comparison.

	isolated		monolayer				
	β	η	β	η	β_z	η_z	a_β
$\lambda_{inc} = \infty$							
AZO-H(E)*	3156		3001 ± 494		-2268 ± 609		1.92 ± 3.15
AZO-H(Z)*	1373	2.3	1574 ± 485	1.91	-1308 ± 436	1.73	2.89 ± 3.63
AZO-A(E)	8497		8026 ± 1198		-4556 ± 1430		0.76 ± 0.36
AZO-A(Z)	2904	2.9	2805 ± 1190	2.86	-1349 ± 1428	3.38	0.90 ± 1.10
AZO-D(E)	723		1075 ± 463		785 ± 496		1.87 ± 2.09
AZO-D(Z)	1427	0.5	1292 ± 324	0.83	126 ± 670	6.23	0.60 ± 0.70
$\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm							
AZO-H(E)*	11490		10842 ± 2976		-8044 ± 2915		1.75 ± 2.11
AZO-H(Z)*	3081	3.7	4442 ± 2314	2.44	-3629 ± 1865	2.22	2.77 ± 3.19
AZO-A(E)	46956		51647 ± 21810		-30133 ± 14905		0.80 ± 0.37
AZO-A(Z)	8457	5.6	12255 ± 10875	4.21	-6133 ± 7961	4.91	0.93 ± 1.24
AZO-D(E)	5617		5449 ± 3371		3431 ± 3243		1.42 ± 1.48
AZO-D(Z)	3279	1.7	4435 ± 3219	1.23	170 ± 3177	20.18	0.66 ± 0.92

* Values taken from Ref. 24.

The static and dynamic values of the total first hyperpolarizability (β), averaged over the dynamics, do not deviate much from the values calculated for the molecules in their equilibrium geometry, despite significant geometrical distortions are observed on the SAMs. As a consequence, the static and dynamic $\eta = \beta(E)/\beta(Z)$ contrasts follow the same trends, with the contrasts normal to the surface plane ($\eta_z = \beta_z(E)/\beta_z(Z)$) for AZO-H and AZO-A having the same magnitude as the total ones. The situation is different for AZO-D, for which η_z is as large as 6.2 in the static case and reaches 20.2 in the dynamic regime, mainly owing to the very weak NLO response of the Z isomer. However, although a high η_z contrast is a key specification for the design of NLO switchable 2D devices, the AZO-D system does not appear promising for such applications. Indeed, as shown in Figure 9, the β_z distributions of the E and Z forms largely overlap, which is detrimental to the reading process, as the variation of the NLO signal may not be experimentally distinguishable. Reversely, AZO-A exhibits promising features, as -NO₂ substitution enhances the η_z contrast with respect to the non-substituted system, while E and Z isomers keep well-separated ranges of β_z values.

Table 3 also reveals the large impact of the chemical substitution on the NLO anisotropy. Regardless of the isomeric state, for the non-substituted system AZO-H, anisotropy factors a_β are found larger than 1.0, while they are all below 1.0 for AZO-A, indicating that in the latter case the in-plane β components dominate over the normal one. As discussed in the next section, this can be related to the larger tilt of the AZO-R units with respect to the surface plane (see Table 1), which enhances the in-plane β components. Moreover, quite counter-intuitively, in both AZO-H and AZO-A, the anisotropy factors are larger for the Z form, suggesting an increase of the normal NLO signal upon photoisomerization. However, these results should be taken with caution, since the a_β distributions are very broad, with in most cases standard deviations larger than the average values. Conversely, in the case of AZO-D, an opposite variation in the NLO anisotropy is observed upon photoisomerization, the a_β factor being larger than 1 for E and lower for Z. Interestingly, as this quantity is accessible from polarization-resolved SHG experiments, such variation could also be exploited to probe

the isomerization state of the SAM.

To further investigate the links between the geometrical structures of the AZO residues and the NLO properties of the SAMs, we monitored the variation of the SH responses with electronic and structural parameters of the AZO residues, without however finding any clear structure-property relationship. Correlations between β_z and the angles characterizing the orientation of the AZO cores in the SAMs were nevertheless observed in some systems (see Section 4.5 of the SI for details).

3.3.3 Effects of intermolecular electrostatic interactions

The NLO properties discussed so far were obtained from calculations on isolated molecules, without considering any intermolecular interactions. Herein, the intermolecular electrostatic interactions are included by the implementation of a point-charge (PC) embedding in the DFT calculations (see Section 2.6). In Figures 10 and 11 we analyze the effect of this embedding on the distributions of the dynamic NLO properties, comparing with those obtained without embedding. Interestingly, the impact of the embedding depends on the nature of the R-group. In the case of AZO-A, the electrostatic interactions induce a lowering of β and β_z , of both the isomeric forms of the SAMs, while the NLO anisotropy a_β is essentially unchanged. The much larger weakening of the interfacial NLO signal found for AZO-A(E) compared to AZO-A(Z) can be explained by the larger dipole moment of the *trans* isomers (see Table 2), and by their more parallel alignment. An opposite effect is observed in the case of AZO-D SAMs, in which the norm of the interfacial NLO response of both the *trans* and *cis* forms increases in the presence of the PC-Embedding. These opposite results can be ascribed to the electrostatic potential due to the ALK portion, which is globally positively charged ($\sim +0.3e$) regardless of the nature of the R group or the E/Z conformation of the azobenzene. This positive charge environment experienced by the photochromic units induces a lowering of the intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) when the azobenzene core is substituted by an electron acceptor group in its opposite 4' position, while the ICT is instead

enhanced in the case of substitution with a donor group.

Table 4: Average values and standard deviations of the static ($\lambda_{inc} = \infty$) and dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) NLO responses of PC-Embedded AZO molecular residues for the different monolayers: $(\beta)_{env}$, $(\beta_z)_{env}$ and $(a_\beta)_{env}$ and hyperpolarizability contrasts, defined as $(\eta)_{env} = (\beta(E))_{env}/(\beta(Z))_{env}$ and $(\eta_z)_{env} = (\beta_z(E))_{env}/(\beta_z(Z))_{env}$. The results obtained in Ref. 24 for the non-substituted SAMs are also reported for comparison.

	$(\beta)_{env}$	$(\eta)_{env}$	$(\beta_z)_{env}$	$(\eta_z)_{env}$	$(a_\beta)_{env}$
$\lambda_{inc} = \infty$					
AZO-H(E)*	2200 ± 704		-1614 ± 693		1.79 ± 2.55
AZO-H(Z)*	1174 ± 402	1.87	-893 ± 375	1.81	2.27 ± 2.87
AZO-A(E)	4582 ± 1477		-2230 ± 771		0.66 ± 0.34
AZO-A(Z)	2480 ± 1005	1.85	-767 ± 1105	2.91	0.71 ± 1.03
AZO-D(E)	1479 ± 812		733 ± 1036		1.57 ± 1.53
AZO-D(Z)	1708 ± 486	0.87	537 ± 802	1.36	0.60 ± 0.71
$\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm					
AZO-H(E)*	7703 ± 3675		-5620 ± 3166		1.81 ± 2.42
AZO-H(Z)*	3380 ± 1722	2.28	-2609 ± 1450	2.15	2.40 ± 3.22
AZO-A(E)	24259 ± 13563		-12957 ± 6458		0.77 ± 0.36
AZO-A(Z)	10955 ± 9673	2.21	-4083 ± 7332	3.17	0.85 ± 1.38
AZO-D(E)	8087 ± 5793		2662 ± 6680		1.52 ± 1.67
AZO-D(Z)	6079 ± 3936	1.33	1705 ± 3494	1.56	0.67 ± 1.41

* Values taken from Ref. 24.

Figure 10: Distributions of the dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) β , β_z and a_β values of isolated molecules (*isol*) and PC-Embedded molecules (*env*) for the two isomers of AZO-A. Average values and standard deviations are also reported. Static results are reported in the SI.

Figure 11: Distributions of the dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) β , β_z and a_β values of isolated molecules (*isol*) and PC-Embedded molecules (*env*) for the two isomers of AZO-D. Average values and standard deviations are also reported. Static results are reported in the SI.

4 Conclusions

The nonlinear optical properties of self-assembled monolayers based on substituted azobenzene photoswitches were obtained with a combination of classical molecular dynamics simulations and quantum chemistry calculations. Two different chemical *para*-substitutions of the azobenzene units were considered, either an electron-acceptor nitro group (AZO-A) or an electron-donating primary amine (AZO-D) in both their *trans* and *cis* isomeric forms.

The morphology of the monolayers was characterized by considering separately the alkyl chain segment and the photoswitchable fragment: the former shows a well-defined alignment with an upright tilted orientation deviating by approximately 14-20° from the surface normal. On the contrary, the AZO portion shows a very broad distribution of the tilt angles and a much higher positional disorder, independently from the isomerization state or the nature of the chemical substituent, with the largest disorder registered for AZO-D.

Interestingly, despite the large geometrical distortions observed for the AZO sublayer in all the SAMs, the static and dynamic contrast of the first hyperpolarizability (η) and of its normal component (η_z) show the same trend as the ones computed for the derivatives in

their equilibrium geometry, suggesting that a screening on isolated molecules could be useful to anticipate the variation in the NLO responses of the SAMs upon photoswitching. Compared to the pristine azobenzene SAMs, *para*-substitution increases the η_z contrast for both nitro and amino substituents. However, only nitro-substitution leads to an increase of the response of the stable *trans* form, while it decreases dramatically with amino-substitution. This weakening of the NLO activity combined with the large overlap of the distributions of the β responses of the *trans* and *cis* forms suggests that *para*-NH₂ substitution is not promising for application in NLO-switchable 2D devices. Finally, the inclusion of the electrostatic embedding leads in general to a reduction of the computed NLO response, whose extent seems to be correlated with the polarity of the environment. More quantitative approaches to describing environment effects should nevertheless involve the use of polarizable embedding schemes or full quantum approaches on finite-size clusters extracted from the MD trajectories. Further work along these lines is in progress.

Supporting Information Available

Additional data on the parametrization of the force field, the structural analysis of the SAMs, and the computation of the NLO responses.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the French National Research Agency (grant number ANR-20-CE29-0009-01), as well as by the Transnational Common Laboratory QuantumChemPhys (*Theoretical Chemistry and Physics at the Quantum Scale*, grant number ANR-10-IDEX-03-02) established between the Université de Bordeaux (UB), Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea (UPV/EHU) and the Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC). We also acknowledge financial support from MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 (projects PID2022-136231NB-I00 and RED2024-154178-T) and by the Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER).

Calculations were performed using the computing facilities provided by the Mésocentre de Calcul Intensif Aquitain (MCIA) of UB and of the Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour and the Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC) Computer Center, whose technical supports are gratefully acknowledged.

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